

DIALECT AND APPROACH IN THE TIME OF INTERNATIONAL MASS MEDIA

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6571505>

Rakhmatova E'zoza Otabek qizi

2nd-course student Uzbek State World Languages University

Azizov Ulugbek Botirovich

scientific advisor

Masters department

Uzbek State World Languages University

Annotation: *Assuming one ought to participate in a discussion about what there is to know concerning the consistently changing world that comes the way cleared with vulnerabilities and globalization, it is an extremely mind-boggling undertaking to figure out something worth agreeing on. Particularly, managing sciences like Linguistics and Stylistics it is extremely challenging to track down the specific contentions to demonstrate the laid out proposition. The point of this paper is to attempt to demonstrate our proposal that language and its style are profoundly impacted or better, tainted, by worldwide broad communications correspondence. Many all-around regarded writers have been expounding on this issue. Be that as it may, this is an open field of vulnerabilities. Managing, in our exploration, with the essential issue of how worldwide broad communications impact language and its style and the idea of verbal correspondence of divided man of the postmodern time, we, at the same time, attempt to open the stage for future, more broadened, research in this field.*

Keywords: *language, style, globalization, mass media, public communication*

Introduction. The way into the endurance of man in the worldwide society is "the safe identity". Notwithstanding, Scholte in his book "Globalization a Critical Introduction" finishes up that "for an individual to be untroubled on the planet he or she wants an acceptable thought about who will be who, where he has a place, what he needs to turn out to be, along with the conviction that the general public will regard and protect these ways of being, having a place and accomplishing. Individual character is ignored in the worldwide society. It has lost its essential common and social worth." Modern globalization has likewise now and again subverted the well-being of character through social obliteration. Different life universes quailed before they invade electronic broad communications, transplanetary the travel industry, worldwide English language, industrialism and other sub-regional mediations which go against the nearby custom. The world's greatest media offices produce on one way or then again the other, the rearrangements of societies and the osmosis of ways of life. Be that as it may, not to wander from the subject of the paper any further, language and with it, the style has

affected all things considered. Close to half of the dialects individuals use all over the planet will before long quit being utilized. Some etymologists even think that very nearly the vast majority of the dialects of the world will stop existing during the XXI century. Scholte claims that this advancement is advanced by the worldwide media by giving genuine importance just to the major world dialects. The pattern of homogenization of culture and language as well as worldwide westernization influences the mass feeling of loss of character and confidence. The social issues concerning language additionally make critical orders in globalization the board. The standard of western dialects, particularly English, definitely causes different countries to feel underrated.^[19] Moreover, the thoughts and standards which are not effectively deciphered in English are regularly challenging to push forward for a conference at worldwide discussions. On the other hand, all that boundless public and worldwide obliviousness also lack involvement just invigorate the hostility of public media which influence the production of correspondence mumbles. Strategies System of language-expressive examination in the field of media in a worldwide time depends on the lingual-elaborate investigation as the essential technique for a worldwide informative talk. Too, the strategy for allowance and synthesis went with similar exploration are remembered for the examination interaction. Because of its discoveries, we foster the further association of the text. Conversation The instructive and social circle of activity in the worldwide age that capacities for the most part as indicated by the standards of the western model has neither time nor ear, and most certainly, has no tolerance for various or unique world sees. The non-western models can cause a brief remark by the decision worldwide culture without entering any further into the deeper layers of what is said, composed, or shown. The standard of the English language on the planet makes it incomprehensible for the enormous piece of mankind to communicate its thoughts and be engaged with the changing and making of the worldwide world. The broad communications influence the development of casual state-funded schooling by tending to a great many data. Individuals in the world ought to get more familiar with globalization and its key desires, necessities, needs, plans from those sources. Be that as it may, very little is found out about these issues from the media, since they simply don't see an explanation or then again interest in coordinating the consideration towards globalization as a peculiarity and, then again, they purposefully keep away from instructing the majority on this peculiarity. One reason is that the media are don't know about which heading ought to be taken or then again if the ascent in the instructive level in this space may undermine their advantages.

Columnists themselves have regularly an exceptionally unfortunate instruction in the space of globalization so that even, when they get the opportunity to expound on it, they don't have the foggiest idea how to approach the subject, because, aside from their

¹⁹ Avramović S. Rhetoric Techno / S. Avramović. – Beograd: Službeni glasnik, 2008.

unfortunate information, their composing pens are not adequately sharp. Numerous media reports and media channels carelessly underline the predominant new liberal ways to deal with globalization from one viewpoint, and on the other hand, the media has a place with a huge business that benefits from advancement and privatization in the space of correspondence. The principal media bodies are likewise firmly associated with the circles in power and that likewise influences the quality and objectivity of insightful news coverage. The mass media play a key part in keeping individuals all over the planet oblivious and deceive about the significant inclinations of the worldwide impact the postmodern age has on them. This condition in the worldwide world altogether impacts the columnists who feel the limitation and the absence of opportunity to respond as indicated by the directors of their calling, morals, and individual convictions. "For specific agents to be viewed as liable for something they should have a comprehension of key moral thoughts like equity, and moral responses like applause and judgment. Such arrangement doesn't need to be profound, in any case, without a more extensive thought about those sizes, the man will not be dependable." The opportunity to communicate his thoughts unequivocally through language has a place with the individual. In this case, the writer, ought to have the unconstrained mindfulness about his obligation to himself and the world. Such opportunity is acquired through the fortitude to communicate a certain mentality regardless of the abstract sensation of being compelled. There is a notable instance of the writer who worked at the renowned high-course day by day the New York Times who created his reports, reports, interviews utilizing modern dialect and style. He made it happen

effectively for very nearly six years taking care of the readers' craving for augmented reality.^[20]

The primary example of the worldwide society is contained writers becoming acquainted with dragging out their controls in conveying the reality and adjusting the crowd to deceptions. Language and it's going with instruments conceal the genuine data and show the bogus ones. E. Kant proposes that we stay as distant as we can from propensities since they severely limit our independence and our freedom. The worldwide man is experiencing like never before from propensities since those propensities are generally conventionalist. Propensities influence the opportunity of the human soul to make its style. Is man himself not the style, as Buffon composed? If a man has the propensity for enduring five to seven hours observing one of the splendid screens, he opens himself to avoid shallow language. Roland Bart addresses the assessment that language is a sort of reaction, a show, and that behind the language there is a style that comes from the man's inborn and procured properties. He immovably accepts that style doesn't have a place with language. As per him style is outside of language and is just a

²⁰ Cassirer E. Filozofija simboličnih formi / E. Cassire. – Novi Sad: Književna zajednica, 1985.

going with object. Broad communications, deliberately or not, in its endeavor to work on language, keep the style on separation from language. Public discourse, for old Greeks, was the premise of a majority rule government and opportunity. Sreten Petrovic discusses a rationale ethic and an officially stylish division which, every one in its particular manner, characterize and pass judgment on the deliberateness of the manner of speaking. The main current discusses stressing and communicating reality through language, and the other addressed by the critics is centered around cajoling and influence and on the magnificence and style of articulation (the way something is said not what is said). Plato never gave credit to the way of talking as a method nor as workmanship. He called the skeptics toadies whose main design was to be loved by the group rather than sustaining reality. Aristotle attempted to join these two flows by adding another component of confirmation as a way to lighten the manipulative force of cajoling and influence and to draw nearer to the rationale ethic current to whom talking the reality of the situation was vital.

One of the best rationalists of the XX century E. Cassirer claims that language becomes one of the rudimentary "profound means through which there is an advancement from the simple universe of feeling to the universe of insight and execution. Shuvakovic, then again, discusses an evolving construction of current human advancement which is portrayed by the nonattendance of a remarkable philosophy, comprehension of the language as per its entomb language capacities and not as per the reference to the world external the language, the metabolization, an allegorization of portrayal. Then again, talking about a style of correspondence in the time of globalization means to talk about the progress from the person to the system. Myers and Myers express that correspondence addresses a focal peculiarity of culture. Likewise, assuming that we get correspondence as an emblematic cycle, in which the human mindfulness is made, kept up with, fixed, and changed, all of this could squeeze into the meaning of world worldwide correspondence. Correspondence and broad communications are incredibly answerable for the advancement of restricted language abilities, particularly among youngsters. John Street states in his book Mass Media, Politics and Democracy, that broad communications effect raising the mindfulness about political education of residents all over the planet and TV has more effect on the watchers' feelings, however simultaneously, TV influences individuals so that they shut themselves out from social casings. Robert Putnam states in the very book that "consistently a watcher spends staring at the TV is connected with his lesser trust in the social climate. TV, as a private amusement, expands the opposition towards the rest of the world and debilitates residents' commitment to the social framework. Clearly language, as a social classification, deteriorate in a current culture where everybody is caught up with checking the screens out rather than having alive preservation. Stylistics as a youthful science manages the method of the connection between the individual and the general public in the specific circumstance of the purpose of language inside the edge

of common correspondence. The expressiveness of language can be the result of a spiritualized, free view on life, not the persecuted or then again controlled view that broad communications make. Talbot Taylor planned the hypothesis of style as the hypothesis of correspondences. As per him the course of correspondence can't be clarified exclusively by dry semantic speculations that fundamentally clarify the verbal correspondence as to the theoretical connection of articulation and significance. This sort of analysis imperils the idea of a connection between language and correspondence. The messages we get in any correspondence impact correspondence more than their meaning.^[21]

In the public media where language is utilized each day to express various perspectives and feelings the assessment of the nature of data is vital. How data is gotten relies upon the way the writer utilizes language. The language utilized by the media must go against the language of writing, regarding the authenticity of normalized language, and that isn't consistently the case as we will see later in this text. The deficiency of personality and independence in the worldwide time of media, political and social savagery achieves the debilitating and ignoring of the singular's style. The columnist stands out no more as a maker, an author, or an evaluator of the real world. He doesn't lay out, through his style, an extraordinary, remote contact with his perusers or watchers however, tragically, rather he frames a far-off, formal, and alienated contact. Language culture in worldwide, public composed media in Serbia and the abnormalities that happen day by day in open media has been composed every once in a while by Egon Fekete, Ivan Klein, Serbian language specialists, Milovan Danojlic, the author who composed the renowned book *Torment with words* in 1975. Logical papers have been perused in logical meetings also distributed in magazines and compilations. What gets the eye in the majority of them are, separated the language anomalies, the accentuation on the expanding mastery of administrative language. The most frequently referenced models are the utilization of disintegrated predicate (give an idea - recommend), give assessment - think), give commitment - contribute), nominalization of explanations, utilization of "ing" word in various case developments: two maps traded assessments, there were conversations, counsels were made, and so on The most unsettling is the way that separated from writers, legislators and well-known people who utilize the administrative language its utilization is more regular inconsistent discourses. What delivers a particular alert is simply youthful individuals utilize this type of non-standard language.

The investigation of expanding presence of regulatory language which hinders and abuses the physiognomy of the normalized language appears to fail to focus on language being over each of the social classes. Aside from lingual variables, there are likewise non-lingual factors that influence its turn of events. The presence of the way of life of mass

²¹ Lešić Z. *Teorija književnosti / Z. Lesic.* – Beograd: Zavod za izdavanje udžbenika, 2010.

society got an aggravation in the advancement inclinations of the spoken language. It upset the real language culture in connection to the language truth of the ineffectively instructed. These changes keep on impacting the language culture of all layers and ages in the general public with expanded power nearly day by day. Indeed, even individuals with ideal information on the guidelines of normalized language, practical styles, and who consider themselves elaborately proficient, can't handle the monolingual driving forces that influence language. The analysis of the culture of mass society comes from both, the conservatives and the radicals. The initial ones dread insurgency being the outcome of mass society, and the other ones accept that mass culture is a result of the decision class what's more that it invigorates the middle-class esteem framework. Language as a vital job in each social practice, related to phonetic implications is conclusive because it is impacted not simply by the maker yet additionally by the translator. Each importance has its account rationale has its own story about itself and others. Semantics and stylistics give a fair premise to the deconstruction of the power that makes a stage expected for the utilization of non-legitimate discourse; the regulatory language being one of them. Roland Bart addresses the general population with the investigation of culture as a text. As indicated by him all that is broadcast through broad communications are exposed to perusing because it is a result of a marking cycle. The semiology approach assumes that social texts are a sign of social designs which are widespread, unchangeable and that the cycle of naming is dynamic 100% of the time. Be that as it may, in actuality, in the field, each event has a bunch of implications. Hence the peculiarity of intersexuality appears.^[22]

It endeavors to pass on each importance open to new and unique understandings. His popular hypothesis about the creator's passing affirms the position that there isn't a peculiarity or implying that can be deciphered in a manner its creator wants rather the importance gets its worth just when it is deciphered or on the other hand different by the beneficiary or the purchaser. This intends that the interests of strong ideologists can be diverted and additionally the postulation of certain scholars like Sandra Sharon's that administrative language is forced by the focuses of force, states, the older sibling and so on On the off chance that we "decipher" Bart's understanding of culture as a text there is one obvious message, the translator of the restricted and unfortunate message can't truly improve his language and style. The writer in her book *The most effective method to Write for the Newspaper* offers guidance to the present and future writers, but to the specialists too: Remember that every one of the legislatures and administrations of the world will attempt to cause their work to appear less clear because the confusion of the work is a compelling method for administering without responsibility. An optimal method for that object is language. In this manner, it doesn't make any difference if the massive language of organization is utilized or the language out of which God's

²² Radovanović M. Sociolingvistika / M. Radovanovic. – Beograd: Nolit, 1980.

substance talks, or the desire of individuals, or the power of the political way of thinking, human science, brain research, economy, regulation or some other previous livelihood of the government officials... The language of the organization is ideally perceived if it isn't heard in any way. Subsequently, you should attempt to comprehend what the public authority is doing before locking in in political news coverage. What is of no less significance is this: you ought to set free of the dread from the public authority up not to become befuddled by its language. You are passed on to battle with the administrations of different jobs. You wouldn't accept however there are however numerous as there may be unique callings. For what reason do individuals talk and compose administratively? Can they oppose the negative impact of broad communications on their language? The control of people, in general, wouldn't be imaginable without the public's assent. Picking a lesser detestable, just in the general public controlled by political dread, implies consenting to control. In any remaining cases language offers to general society something that it needs, something that it needs, or something to that effect it appreciates. What does he respect and what does he exceptionally appreciate in an administrative talk? The general public can have various qualities at various times and these days the principle values are generally western qualities and advancement.

Likewise, since the start of the cutting edge age, the public has had a high incentive for objective logical comprehension. Regulatory way of talking today appropriates unfamiliar words from western governmental issues and economy (for the most part English words) and certain highlights of the logical style". The substance of post-structuralism is that there is no objective reality that has not gone through the implications given by the language. J. Derrida believes that it is impossible to decide reality because each verbally expressed word conveys the hints of what was left implicit. Maybe Foucault would be a superior model for understanding the issue we are managing. He isn't keen on the working of the actual language however he is intrigued by the social circumstances which lead to the formation of verbose information. As indicated by him the actual discourse is not critical to society in any case, who is talking and why. The delegates of broad communications realize that all around well that the esteem framework is relative and variable which is the reason all through mankind's set of experiences different desultory arrangements were prevailing, arrangements that control a specific arrangement of information which couldn't measure up to whatever was or that is yet to be. Language is variable on a schedule comparable to the new and eccentric circumstances. Reception of models and examples for their utilization and working in correspondence doesn't occur as indicated by a specific example. Each member in correspondence has language capacity, and the method of conveying relies upon the ability of the code and correspondence. Correspondence mumbles have an impressive impact on the course of correspondence (lacking consideration, philosophical decisions, apathy, and so on) An optimal discourse agent (in the sense assumed by the

delegates of generative language) who has no such thing as ideal language information. He particularly does not exist among the utilized in the broad communications where no formal training is expected for the gig.^[23] Language is variable on a schedule comparable to the new and flighty circumstances. Reception of models and examples for their utilization and working in correspondence doesn't occur as per a specific example. Each member in correspondence has language capacity, and the method of imparting relies upon the ability of the code and correspondence. Correspondence mumbles have a significant impact on the course of correspondence (deficient consideration, philosophical decisions, detachment, and so on) An optimal discourse delegate (in the sense assumed by the agents of generative language structure) who has no such thing as ideal language information. He particularly does not exist among the utilized in the broad communications where no formal training is expected for the gig. The event of discourse is an intricate course of correspondence that relies upon the expressed circumstance (a non-lingual setting). For similar columnists, different spoken circumstances could be questioners with various pieces of training, philosophies, attitudes, the availability for a substantial discussion, stage dismay, and so forth A Serbian sociolinguist Radovanovic says: The discourse illustrative has the standards for picking and utilizing language instruments relying upon the sort of phonetic circumstances along with any remaining principles in the part of his insight about a language called the capability of correspondence Since no discourse shows itself as a bound together entire however rather it changes contingent upon who addresses whom, with what reason and so forth Subsequently, a discourse variety happens which has its style trademark among others. One of the fundamental purposes behind such an event is that the useful delineation of language isn't normatively managed. Henceforth the carelessness in the utilization of language. Numerous editors of the public media don't know nor are they natural with the discourse varieties or practical styles. Very much like lawful guideline achieved progress a sort of guideline would acquire changes language too. Thusly, Radovanovic recommends: A language standard should expressly bring up the semantic highlights of a style and indicate which non-lingual conditions are required for their decision and use. A few hypothetical premises are normal for sociolinguistics and psycholinguistics in the phonetic work furthermore activities they embrace. For instance, one of them notices language not just in the efficient circle as semantic information for example capability, yet additionally in the communicational circle as determined by Radovanovic. Very significant issues are connected with the issue of language procurement, bilingualism, diglossia, and multilingualism in discourse communications of any sort, association and capacity of the discourse act, the relationship between's etymological, social, social, and mental designs and events, character structures, discourse act and its incorporation on the level of talk, etymological activities in the space of broad communications and so on.

²³ Svendsen L.F.H. *Filozofija slobode* / L.F.H Svendsen. – Beograd: Geopoetika, 2013.

Language itself and its expressive activities can't be confined from its regular habitat and social and social setting and be perceived and deciphered by shut, conceptual, and generalized equations. There are no homogeneous language articulations any semblance of which the delegates of customary etymology are attempting to depict. Language, as indicated by Georgas Mooning isn't prepared in a way that it can convey the most unimaginable experience of the individual communicating in the language. The intricacy of the language capacities ought to be fathomed as a reality which cautions us that it relies upon the specific acknowledged discourse event and discourse activities inside it when and in which explanation a portion of the potential elements of language may progressively get to the very front. Neither structuralisms nor generativists made the circumstances to notice language in the entirety of human correspondence exercises, social, social, mental, and different cooperations or even contrast language with them. Lesic here poses the key inquiry, basing his presumptions on Plato's and Aristotle's hypothesizes about style. To demonstrate his postulation on the solidarity of thought and discourse he proposed a unit he showed up at during the investigation that contains the properties inborn to discourse thought as solidarity. That unit would as per him be the importance of the words, since significance is neither discourse nor thought, and they create and change through history. Aside from every one of the recorded potential reasons that lead to the bountiful utilization of the regulatory style in open media and by the student's writers to be well-known individuals, different reasons could be added like the advancement of innovations, the quantity of data which duplicate by mathematical movement, the supplanting of words with pictures, not perusing and forceful legislative issues of the proprietors and chiefs of broad communications and so on.^[24] Vigotsky immovably dismisses the lessons of prior schools about the association among word and importance being just affiliated and made under the various matching in the awareness of the impression created by the word and the impression made by the item for which the word represents.

Administrative language and its style isn't just an exchange of the regulatory bogeyman from the famous communism in Yugoslavia yet additionally, and numerous genuine language epicureans settle on it Fekete, Klajn, Danojlic, also others that this language "the new discourse" of the worldwide age has every one of the components of a similarly restricted discourse of which Orwell composed and the circumstances for its application have at long last been met in this time of broad communications. Words have, as indicated by A. Alonso irresistible power that must be considered by the people who manage stylistics. We should stop here briefly, and consider that irresistible enthusiasm of words when regulatory language is concerned. Clean students demonstrated in the paper "Зуцие Варсзawy" how demagogic and buzzword language can be. They made a table with four-level segments and ten vertical sections. There are a

²⁴ Šuvaković M. Postmoderna / M.Šuvaković. – Beograd: Narodna knjiga, 1995.

couple of words in every section from the regulatory pointless word reference from the hour of communist Poland. Sima Avramovic in his book Rhetoric techno refers to this model as a brilliant sign of void regulatory words that can assist with making more than 10,000 unique talks. Every single one of them sounds genuine and critical however, truth be told they don't say anything. These backslide from the past tracked down their place in the present worldwide composed media. Sima Avramovic calls those phonetic phrases mantras and fetishes. Language of the worldwide age has its fixations, thoughts, for example, Human freedoms, ethnic purging, the market economy, worldwide society, orientation accuracy, resilience, multiethnic and so on Numerous different terms, large numbers of which come from the administrative word reference of global foundations and worldwide world organization, are coming into use and isolating individuals to the people who are educated and the people who are not. The utilization of some of those terms is a decent base for control and demagoguery by the people who got comfortable with the words first thus acquiring the option to decipher their importance to those new to them. It is a delicate issue, particularly when terms don't have exactly resolved implications. Right alongside it comes the creation of assent through media promulgation hardware. The most uncommon delineation of it is presumably the continually rehashed sentence by Margaret Thatcher when she talked about the certainty of neoliberals - there is no other option. As per Avramovic, regulatory language incorporates mottos, undesired and illegal words, neologisms, phrases. The regulatory language of contemporary media stifles the individual, and it promotes the market and the political tip top. Demagogic shading of such a language is one of the primary dangers to present-day vote-based systems and opportunities in the worldwide world. "Subsequently, maybe, one might say that authoritarianism starts in the language," Sima Avramovic took note.

Conclusion. We attempted to, by referring to various creators' hypotheses and thoughts connected with the broad communications in worldwide time, join the individuals who address an exceptionally intricate subject that has not been examined much. The control of broad communications in every aspect of human worldwide life makes a vacuum in which the western progress makes progress toward a super chronicled fancy that more data and shallow information drives that very human progress along the correct way. On the off chance that language, as the embodiment of all correspondence, gets snatched by forceful and shallow objectives of broad communications and its makers, an individual of (post)modern time will be secured hard of hearing society. An interesting individual will eventually in a blended voice utter certain words expressing and expressing don't however say anything. Then, at that point, it will be passed the point of no return for any activity.

REFERENCES:

1. Avramović S. Rhetoric Techno / S. Avramović. – Beograd: Službeni glasnik, 2008.
2. Cassirer E. Filozofija simboličnih formi / E. Cassire. – Novi Sad: Književna zajednica, 1985.
3. Cvetanović I. In Fieri / I.Cvetanovic. – Niš: NKC, 2012.
4. Lešić Z. Teorija književnosti / Z. Lesic. – Beograd: Zavod za izdavanje udžbenika, 2010.
5. Petrovic S. Retorika / S. Petrovic. – Nish: Gradina, 1975.
6. Radovanović M. Sociolingvistika / M. Radovanovic. – Beograd: Nolit, 1980.
7. Svendsen L.F.H. Filozofija slobode / L.F.H Svendsen. – Beograd: Geopoetika, 2013.
8. Scholte J.A. Globalizacija / J.A. Scholte. – Podgorica: CID, 2009.
9. Share S. Kako pisati za medije / S.Share. – Beograd: Mediacentar, 2001.
10. Šuvaković M. Postmoderna / M.Šuvaković. – Beograd: Narodna knjiga, 1995.
11. Vuković N. Stilističke ideje / N.Vuković. – Beograd: Jasen, 2001.
12. Street J. Mass media politics and democracy / J. Street. – New York: Palagrane, 2001.